

Desert Stars VR: A case study on audience reception of virtual reality experience to raise awareness of the Sahrawi traditional astronomical knowledge and the Western Sahara conflict

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In this paper, we examine the exhibition of the Desert Stars VR, a component from the transmedia narrative Desert Stars, an outcome of the co-creation process between the Amanar project and the Saharawi community. The products of Desert Stars were developed as part of the Amanar astronomy outreach project that aims to support and inspire the Sahrawi community using astronomy. We focus particularly on the reception of this VR experience by the Sahrawi audience during the FiSahara International Film Festival. Our analysis delves into the feedback from the Sahrawi participants, examining how their reactions and interactions with the VR content reflect broader themes in scientific communication. We assess the successes and challenges encountered throughout this project, providing insights into how these experiences can inform future virtual reality applications in astronomy outreach. This discussion aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of how immersive technologies can be leveraged to enhance science communication and engage diverse audiences in meaningful ways.

Introduction

Since 1975, hundreds of thousands of Sahrawis have been living in camps near Tindouf, Algeria, making the Sahrawi refugee situation one of the most prolonged in the world. Among the many programmes supporting the Sahrawi community, many indicators suggest that the resolution to refugee situations requires not only

humanitarian interventions but also development-led action (*World Bank, 2017*).

The Amanar project¹ (*Benítez-Herrera & Rivero-González, 2020; Benítez-Herrera et al., 2020; Carrelli et al., 2022*) – organised by the volunteer outreach initiative GalileoMobile (*Benítez-Herrera & Spinelli, 2015*) – aims to support and inspire the Sahrawi community using astronomy. Amanar pays special attention to Sahrawi

children and youth to awaken their interest in science, stimulate their imagination and critical thinking and enhance their resilience. The project also promotes mutual understanding and cultural exchange through studying and preserving the rich Sahrawi astronomical traditions and knowledge of the sky.

An important Amanar outcome is the development of the transmedia narrative

Desert Stars². Through interviews with Sahrawi star experts, we recorded conversations via the media of film, audio, photographs and 360-degree immersive videos. Our objective was to support Sahrawis in creating a record of their oral memory and disseminating their astronomical knowledge. In reaching diverse audiences, regardless of their level of access to technology, we aimed to approach scientific knowledge from a decolonial perspective (*Castro-Gómez & Grosfoguel, 2007*).

The original idea was to create a product to popularise the Sahrawi people's knowledge of the sky. However, other demands emerged after talking to star experts and other people from the community using the co-creation process (*Paz & Carrelli, 2022*). It became clear that it was important for them to address their political and social situation. This, in turn, led us to adopt a transmedia strategy, a concept based on the creation and dissemination of different – albeit related – content on different platforms (*Jenkins, 2022*). Based on the specific media, each piece explores a different audience and user experience. Our transmedia narrative was composed of six products: Desert Stars VR (6DoF VR documentary); Desert Stars 360° (3DoF video); Searching for Stars (interactive docu-game); A Refuge in the Stars (feature-length documentary); GalileoCast (podcasts series); Irifi (art gallery installation).

While creating a transmedia narrative requires much more time and resources to be implemented due to its wide scope, we found that it brought three major advantages to our project:

1. Content: by producing more products, we can cover all the topics that emerged during our co-creation process.
2. Aesthetic: transmedia narrative allows us to experiment with different mediums and, consequently, approach different models of scientific communication (*Brossard & Lewenstein, 2010*) in each product.
3. Exhibition: different products can be used in several contexts depending on the resources available in each exhibition venue. For example, Desert Stars 360 (12 minutes long) fits well into activities with children in schools, while A Refuge

in the Stars (69 minutes long) has been shown in lectures and film festivals.

Among the transmedia products worth highlighting is the development of the Desert Stars Virtual Reality (VR)³ experience, which was co-created with the Sahrawi community and focused on raising awareness of both Sahrawi traditional knowledge and the Western Sahara conflict. Different research points out the numerous potential benefits of VR technology in conflict mediation and peacebuilding (UN Department of Political and Peacebuilding Affairs, 2024).

Bringing Desert Stars VR to different communities around the world

Over the past years, the enormous potential of VR in astronomy education and outreach has been well documented (*Impey & Danehy, 2022; Kersting et al., 2023*). During the production of Desert Stars VR, one of the factors discussed was precisely the importance of creating a VR piece that was easily accessible because we intended to include Desert Stars VR as part of the Amanar activities. Therefore, we needed a cost-effective device that would enable us to bring this experience anywhere in the world. That's why we chose the Meta Quest 2 to display our expertise – it is very cheap compared to non-standalone competitors, much simpler to install and set up an exhibition space for a standalone device if we compare it to other more complex headsets⁴ that we have on the market today. This decision proved to be correct not only in our context but also when we began the distribution process at festivals, conferences and other exhibition spaces.

The idea was to create a contemplative experience with several possibilities for interaction so that each participant, upon removing the headset, would have a particular experience depending on the decisions they make within the narrative (i.e., where they look, walk or interact with objects). At the same time, it was important to create narrative mechanisms independent of the participant's interaction so that first-time users would also have a pleasurable experience.

When working with a new technology, creators must be sensitive enough to understand that they are not only presenting content but are often teaching the audience

how to use the new technology. Providing a VR experience to someone for the first time is somehow magical. At the same time, it is a big responsibility since a poor experience can result in motion sickness symptoms such as dizziness, fatigue, headache and nausea that may stop them wanting to use a headset again.

From 2022, we have exhibited Desert Stars VR at 13 venues in Brazil, Japan, Spain and the Sahrawi refugee camps; see Table 1 for more details. We estimate that more than 300 people⁵ experienced Desert Stars VR⁶. This number of views allows us to discuss what worked, what was well received and some difficulties encountered by the public when using the experience. Later in the text, we will use the exhibition at the FiSahara International Film Festival⁷ to describe our impressions.

Desert Stars VR

Desert Stars VR is a six-degree-of-freedom experience, meaning the participant can move and physically walk in the experience. To do that, we needed to create a 3D environment. We chose to use the photogrammetry technique, where producing 3D digital copies of scenes is possible using only 2D images. Through mathematical algorithms, a computer program analyses the common pixels between several images. It detects their position in three-dimensional space, giving rise to point clouds that, in turn, allow the creation of photorealistic 3D models (*Ch'ng et al., 2019*). For this process, a dedicated software called RealityCapture used about 1,300 images of the site to create the 3D scene.

After finishing the retopology process to clean up and reduce the number of triangles needed to visualise the 3D objects to optimise the 3D object for the Meta Quest experience, we added our model to the Unity game engine, where we developed our experience. In Desert Stars VR, we wanted to create a non-linear narrative where participants could explore and interact with the environment in their own time. So, after studying the mechanism and developing the interaction strategy we intended to apply to our experiment, we developed a paper prototype to test this strategy with users before moving forward with the complex programming. This gave us an initial idea of what worked and what

Venue	Location
Bienal de arte Digital	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil – 2022
Centro Federal de Educação Tecnológica, Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro, Universidade Federal do Estado do Rio de Janeiro	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil – 2022 and 2023
Museu de Astronomia e Ciências Afins	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil – 2023
Centro Cultural Banco do Brasil	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil – 2023
Metaversidade	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil – 2023
National Astronomical Observatory of Japan	Tokyo, Japan – 2023
Kavli Institute for the Physics and Mathematics of the Universe	Kashiwa, Japan – 2023
ICIDS 2023 Art Exhibition	Kobe, Japan – 2023
Institute of Heritage Sciences (Incipit-CSIC)	Santiago de Compostela, Spain – 2024
Agrupación Cultural Alexandre Bóveda	A Coruña, Spain – 2024
Institute of Space Sciences (ICE-CSIC)	Barcelona, Spain – 2024
17th Barcelona Science Festival	Barcelona, Spain – 2024
FiSahara International Film Festival 2024	Ausserd, Sahrawi refugee camps near tindouf (Algeria) – 2024

Table 1: List of venues where *Deserts Stars VR* have been exhibited in the period 2022-2024.

we needed to change. Once we found a solution, we tested it before developing it in Unity. This proved to be an efficient way to save production time.

Finally, we ended up with the following experience. Upon entering the three-by-three-metre room where *Desert Stars VR* is set up, the user sits on a carpet with cushions and puts on the VR headset Meta Quest 2. The participant is then transported to a circular courtyard⁸ in the Rabouni protocol centre – the administrative capital of the Sahrawi refugee camps. Sitting on the carpet in front of the participant is the wise Sahrawi Alhaizza⁹ wearing her Melhfa – the traditional Sahrawi One-piece tunic. The scene is illuminated by the light of the stars from the nearby fire. Around, the leaves of the trees sway gently in the wind. Above, the night sky moves slowly, following Earth's rotation. The ambient sounds of the fire, the wind and the goats in the background are spatialised and remain fixed even as the participant moves (Carrelli, 2021).

Figure 1: *Desert Stars VR* Development. From left to right: Original circular courtyard; photogrammetry process to create the 3D model using 2D photos of the original scenario; model applied in Unity game engine and paper prototype used to test the experience with users before further development.

Figure 2: Desert Stars VR scenario.

These first seconds are dedicated to the participant's physical adjustment. Text appears in front of the participant, welcoming them, as suggested on best practices for immersive experiences (Salles & Ruggiero, 2019), giving instructions on how to proceed and how the rules work in this immersive world.

After the first visual impact, we present the participant's role within the narrative through the introductory text inside Desert Stars VR. As we mentioned earlier, interviews with Sahrawi star experts were recorded in audio. With this material, we edited the content and used six audios, around 1-3 minutes long, in Hassaniya Arabic and Spanish, for a virtual reality experience that lasted 10-12 minutes. When the participant approaches the character (represented by a 2D photograph), that person's audio is activated, along with the subtitles available in Portuguese, Spanish, English, and Arabic. In the audio, the visitor is invited to walk around the two-square-metre space

and interact with other characters that appear as the story progresses. The next audio only starts when the previous one ends and if the participant walks towards the next character's photograph. While listening to the audio, the participant can explore the space, interact with objects, and walk around the environment. Raising experience levels through the ability to interact and move (walk) in the scene can increase the participant's sense of immersion and presence (Servotte et al., 2020). In other words, experiencing being in the story instead of just watching it.

Feedback from participation at the FiSahara International Film Festival

Overall, Desert Stars VR was positively received everywhere it was exhibited (see Table 1). In this section, we focus our attention on the participation at the FiSahara International Film Festival because this was an event where we showcased the experience for several days and had more

team members facilitating the experience, making it easier to handle all tasks needed to run the activity. Additionally, the activity included participation from the Sahrawi community.

In early February 2024, the Amanar team received an invitation from the FiSahara International Film Festival to exhibit Desert Stars VR. For the Amanar team, this offered an opportunity to return to the camps to show and see the Sahrawis' reaction to the VR experience. Furthermore, we organised a parallel programme with school activities, teacher training and follow-up work with the Sahrawi researchers performing the ethnoastronomy study about Sahrawi traditional knowledge.

FiSahara reserved a room at the Auserd's Women's House – a community space run by and for Sahrawi women (Cordoba Heredia & Aldana Villalobos, 2021) that is located around the film festival location – where, over six days, Desert Stars VR was shown in eight sessions that lasted

Figure 3: *Magic Room: all set to start the exhibition of Desert Stars VR.*

between two and three hours. The “magic room” was the perfect size for the experience (3.5x3.5m), with a cushion where we established the experience’s starting point. The room was also well-ventilated – which is essential in the desert.

Before arriving at the camps, one of our concerns was the impact of the heat. How would the Meta Quest 2 respond during prolonged use in the heat of the Sahara? Therefore, we took two Meta Quest 2 and brought an extra battery, which can be attached to the headset. This battery is located at the back of the head and proved to be an extremely good idea as it distributes the headset’s weight and temperature. In addition, it comes with a much better strap than the original, making it easier for the participants to put on and take off the headset. Another caution was the hygiene of headsets. After the COVID-19 pandemic, this became an important concern when we think about virtual reality exhibitions. With that in mind, we brought disposable wet wipes to clean the headset display after each use.

Surprisingly, the headset responded very well to the heat. One of the problems with using the headset in hot weather is that it quickly fogs up. However, the lack of humidity in the desert proved to be an ideal place to carry out the activities.

On the first day, after mapping out the room to create the “guardian boundary” (a safe virtual grid designed to display if the user gets too close to the edge of a boundary) and setting up the experiment, we invited a 12-year-old boy to test the experience. At first, the boy was very suspicious. He didn’t speak Spanish, and we didn’t speak Arabic. But after we showed him how it worked, he became curious and decided to try it. At first, he walked carefully, calculating each step. We showed him that he could also pick things up using his virtual hand within the space. After a few tries, he managed to do it, and that really caught his attention. After a few minutes, he asked to take off the headset. He left, then returned with others, adults and children, inviting them to try it. After the others tried, he asked to repeat the experience over and over again. With each attempt, he became increasingly familiar with the technology, testing its limits.

Little by little, he completely mastered it. We later learned that he was the son of one of the women who managed the space. Therefore, he was always around and became an important contributor to the experience. In the following days, he would come back with other friends, and he became our assistant (along with his best friend). When a Sahrawi spoke only Arabic, we called him. He would explain all the steps before starting the experience: where to sit, how to hold the controllers, which

buttons to press, where the person should walk, and even helped the person take off the headset after they finished. This showcases the importance of establishing advocates within a community when introducing a new technology to overcome potential biases audiences might have and even overcome barriers such as the language to facilitate the experience.

This word-of-mouth process that took place on the first day proved to be very effective in promoting the work among the Sahrawi community and also among participants in the FiSahara festival. In total, we showed it to approximately 100 people, with a wide range of ages ranging from a 4-year-old Saharawi girl to a European couple in their 60s.

It was impressive to see that the experience could reach people with different cultural backgrounds and ages (Kersting et al., 2020). Even more enriching was the fact that each person was enchanted by different aspects of Desert Stars VR. In general, adults focused on the story. At the same time, children – most of whom had never used VR before – quickly took ownership of the “game” tools, picking up the virtual objects and throwing them all over the scenario, testing the limits of the experience and looking for bugs in the system. After the initial instructions, we avoided guiding people, leaving them free to interpret the immersive space. However, sometimes, we felt the need to give tips so that the person could move around the space – necessary for the progression of the narrative.

Although we didn’t perform any systematic evaluation, we asked participants to record their feelings after the VR experience on pieces of cardboard that we made available at the entrance to the magic room, see Figure 4.

The messages in Arabic, English and Spanish were positive, ranging from simple thank-you notes to more elaborate messages showcasing their feelings. To highlight one of the most touching messages we received: “This is what we need for the trip.” This participant left his home in Africa when he was a teenager, travelling in a boat through the perilous Atlantic route to arrive in the Canary Islands (Spain), searching for new opportunities in life. He explained that the VR experience

associations and NGOs in support of the Sahrawi community and local astronomical institutions, Amanar organised its summer programme in seven regions in Spain: Canary Islands (Tenerife, La Palma and Gran Canaria), Madrid, Granada, Valencia, A Coruña, Barcelona and Santiago de Compostela. In addition, the Amanar team visited the Sahrawi refugee camps twice in October 2019 and May 2024. During these visits, Amanar organised hands-on activities for students, teacher training and star parties for the whole community. Overall, Amanar has reached over 1,200 Sahrawi children and youth and 100 teachers.

Together with educational activities, Amanar is involved in ethnoastronomical research to preserve Sahrawi astronomical knowledge. In 2019, Amanar started a fruitful collaboration with the Sahrawi Oral History Department to develop an ethnographic study on the traditional knowledge of the sky in Sahrawi. What started with a few interviews with elderly Sahrawis with knowledge of the Sahrawi traditional knowledge of the sky in October 2019 has developed with time into a more structured project with Amanar providing fellowships to support Sahrawi researchers with the compilation and analysis of this ancient knowledge.

² GalileoMobile Transmedia. www.galileomobile.org/desert-stars.

³ Desert Stars VR, 2022 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kHBHJR3FPiI>. Desert Stars is available for free download at: www.galileomobile.org/desert-stars-vr-eng and at: <https://sidequestvr.com/app/7025/desert-stars>.

⁴ Quest 2 is a standalone headset and doesn't require an accompanying PC, whereas other headsets might require being connected to an additional computer, or lightboxes to ascertain position within the virtual space.

⁵ In the SideQuest platform, as of 13 October 2024, the English version had 835 downloads, the Portuguese 89 downloads, the Arabic 146 and the Spanish 53 downloads.

⁶ The number reported refers only to the number of people participating in activities facilitated by Amanar members at the venues listed in Table 1. However, this is a lower limit because the Desert Stars VR experience has been downloaded over 1,000 times by users of VR platforms such as SideQuest where the experience is available for free.

⁷ Created in 2003 by Sahrawis in the camps and Spanish civil society, FiSahara (Western Sahara International Film Festival) is an annual human rights film and cultural festival that seeks to entertain and empower the Sahrawi people through film, as well to raise international awareness about the Western Sahara's ignored conflict.

⁸ This scene was created using the photogrammetry technique, using more than a thousand photographs of the location (other moving elements such as trees, the bonfire and the flag were added later).

⁹ Alhaizza was one of the star experts interviewed during the Amanar project.

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Biographies

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Jorge Rivero González is an astronomer and science communicator and the Head of the Communication and Outreach Office of the Institute of Space Sciences (ICE-CSIC) in Spain. Before that, he coordinated the IAU centenary celebrations in 2019 and participated in the global organisation of the UN's International Year of Light and Technologies based on Light 2015 and UNESCO's International Day of Light. Since 2009, he has been a member of the science outreach programme GalileoMobile.

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Fabio Del Sordo is an Italian astrophysicist working at the Scuola Normale Superiore (Pisa) in Italy. He obtained his PhD at Stockholm University and worked as a researcher in many institutions in Europe and the USA. He is one of the founding members of GalileoMobile.

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